

A ZELUS RENARDII ITALIAN JOURNEY

V. SEFA¹, U. PICCIOTTI², G. RACANIELLO⁴, A. D'ACCOLTI³, L. DIANA¹, F. DUGGAN¹,
V. RUSSO², M. SALERNO², A. LOPEDOTA⁴, N. DENORA⁴, F. PORCELLI^{1,2*}

¹DISSPA UNIBA ALDO MORO, VIA AMENDOLA 165/A - 70126 BARI – ITALY. ²CIHEAM IAMB MEDITERRANEAN AGRONOMIC INSTITUTE OF BARI, VIA CEGLIE 9, 70010 VALENZANO (BA) – ITALY. ³DIRECTA LAB S.R.L., VIA V. SIMPLICIO 45, 70014 CONVERSANO (BA) – ITALY. ⁴DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACY-DRUG SCIENCES, UNIBA ALDO MORO, ITALY.

***Corresponding author: francesco.porcelli@uniba.it**

Any available control action shall compose the frame of a possible IPM strategy devoted to the control of *Philaenus spumarius* Linnaeus, 1758 (Ps), *P. italosignus* Drosopoulos & Remane, 2000, and *Neophilaenus campestris* (Fallén, 1805): these Hemiptera Aphrophoridae were ascertained as vectors (HAV) of *Xylella fastidiosa* pauca ST53, responsible for the Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS) disease now decimating olives in Apulia, South Italy. The knowledge gathered until now may also help to sketch alternative control options in HAV-IPM to preview future unpleasant invasions of different *X. fastidiosa* entities and/or different vectors assemblage. The evidence of HAV population, as the number of individuals per ha living in the OQDS outbreak areas, proves the inadequacy of the vector's Natural Enemies Complex (NEC). In the studies we exploit the *Zelus renardii* Kolenati 1856 (Hemiptera Reduviidae, Zr) potential for HAV biocontrol, based on direct observations and experimental evidence on a total of 1249 individuals. Namely: 487 specimens were collected in nature to study in the laboratory the Zr bionomics and the general predatory behavior; 8, also picked up from nature, to evaluate Zr attitude to prey 1600 offered Ps adults; 754 to study the Zr attitude to mass-breed on living preys or artificial diets in the laboratory. *Zelus renardii* is a stenophagous predator that prefers hemipteran preys of manageable size, also in relation to its size during ontogeny, that includes HAV. Zr if starved and confined in a breeding box can attack and kill honeybees, extra-sized cockroaches, and feed on *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* eggs, but it can also survive on hemipteran honeydew. However, the latter diet does not permit Zr to lay egg batches, while feeding on hemipterans does. In 320 experimental repetitions, we offered 5 Ps per Zr every 24 hours, and the predator caught and killed all of the offered preys in 308 repetitions, leaving one alive in 12 repetitions. Each killing and feeding sequence needed a mean time of 73 min, and the five per day a total mean time of about 6 hours. Zr also re-fed on Ps carcasses. Mass-breeding experiences were carried out on a diets based on living preys (Dm) [*Drosophila melanogaster* (Meigen, 1830), wild type], or artificial diets such as: oligidic (D0, beef liver plus egg yolk homogenate); meridic (D1, D2 & D3, marketed neutral Meritene® or marketed Nidina® 2 OPTIPRO®); and holidic (D4, D0 + D1). The diets were more or less successful: D4 gave the best performance (18,8% of adults) followed by D3 (14,3%) and D0 (= 10,9%). Zr also probes and accepts the diets capsulated in alginate beads, but fails to uptake an appropriate food quantity, partly because of the multi-ocular beads structure and because of the stiff consistency of the shell of the beads. Evidence suggests that Zr is an intriguing biocontrol option for the control of Ps adult vectors, being potentially a good candidate for inoculative release because of its 1) prey range and preference, 2) impact on beneficial, 3) breeding attitude and mass breeding opportunities, and 4) olive secondary pest control attitude. Consequently, we shall consider the use of this biological control option in HAV-IPM.

